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EFFECTIVE PRACTICES OF DISCIPLINING 21ST CENTURY LEARNERS

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It is not surprising for teachers to come across a student with incredible brilliance. Many people believe that today's children are wiser than previous generations. But, when it comes to discipline, is the current generation better than the earlier ones?

Talking about discipline, children nowadays are difficult to please. People may perceive them to be arrogant, naughty, and mischievous, but there is always a reason behind their unruly behavior. These kids might be suffering from disorders such as ADHD, anxiety, autism, etc., that are too difficult for them to handle. Without proper medication and guidance, and assistance from the parents, these children might have trouble with their interpersonal relationships with other people.

The work of a teacher is challenging. Sometimes, the reason behind a child's unruly behavior is not a disorder; it can be what they see in their environment that they only adapt and copy. A teacher's license may be revoked for abuse and harassment if they throw erasers at students, squeeze their ears, or humiliate them in front of the class. These practices did not help students in any way, and they only caused trauma to them. Some say this generation is pro-students, and having these limitations gave them a free pass to do what they want. Nevertheless, there are numerous ways of disciplining children without using violence and humiliating them.

The first one could be informing the parents. Whatever behavior the student does in the class, the parents must be aware of it. Some teachers only report the positive ones. Teachers are expected to act as the second parents for students; thus, when it comes to discipline, parents and teachers should work together. Second, be a good role model. If the teacher is not a good example, the student is impossible to discipline. If a teacher says that everyone should be punctual, he should be punctual too. Lastly, and most important is to communicate with the child. Sometimes, they only wanted to be heard, something they did not usually get at home. Being a child is somehow frustrating because you are only allowed to listen and follow. That is why some children isolate themselves from other kids because adults make them feel unheard.

It could appear like things are in favor of the kids, but it should stay like that. Some practices needed to change to achieve a better outcome. Remember that children are the future of the world. With proper communication with the students and the cooperation of parents, disciplining will not be as demanding as it seems. Teachers are not just responsible for transferring knowledge; they can also teach students value and respect. School should be a safe place for all students where they feel included and

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heard. Even if their home does not feel like a home to them, they at least have somewhere that makes them feel valued.

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